

Rating the Quality in Higher Education

*Vankdoth.Praveen Kumar

Research Scholar Om Prakash Joginder Singh University
Churu Rajasthan

** Dr Prince Bansal

OPJS University
Churu Rajasthan

Abstract:- As a faculty of college and university in India the major components of their career advance is academic performance it also indicates the rate of quality of higher education. So, it has become regulation for standards in higher education. This research paper discusses the API standards of quality in higher education and whether it meets all the guidelines of standards perse? Whether the performance of the teacher in the higher education quantifiable? Whether the quality of the higher education a static variable? As per the UGC regulation minimum qualifications for appointment of academic staff in university and college also maintaining standards in higher education. (4th Amendment) 2016 is discussed in this paper with respect to their question.

Keywords:- API, UGC Regulations, Quality Indicator, Performance Appraisal Higher Education.

I. QUALITY OF HIGHER EDUCATION ONE OF THE GOALS.

The main issues of the higher education India has been approached to equality, Quality Accountability and affordability. This is from very first five year plan to as late as 65th meeting of CABE in 2018, According the goal has set to improve the employability of youth in between age of 18-23 and increase enrollment in higher education enrollment in higher education to 30 by 2030 and prepare 1CR Skilled man power by 2022 65th (CABE). CABE also came forward with the same plan in XII five year plan which there is no significant progress after completing of XII plan period. This could be of many reasons. One of them could be filtering of policy from one level to another level.

This policies followed by legislative. CABE recommendations and five years plan policy are vision level policy. So it is required to follow the second layer policy documents.as per their requirements. The existing policy passed by parliament at nation level is national policy of education (NPE)1986. revised in 1992. NPE suggested to prepare skills manpower at different level which includes research so that development can be take place University grand commission has released few policies issues etc. with the help of (NPE) 1986. If the UGC policy is non in sync it will not get the desired result and if not implemented properly it remain exclusive.

Among all the four issues. This paper has discussed only about the quality of higher education.

II. UGC RULES AND SCHEMES ON QUALITY

The UGC has launched many schemes for enhancement of quality education. some of the UGC schemes are

- 1.(SAP) special assistance programmer
2. (UPE) Universities with potential of excellence
3. (CPEPA) center with potential for excellence in particular area.

The purpose of this schemes.is to development of infrastructure for research. A few schemes provide grants for faculty for, development program, faculty research program, And for some research projects etc. All the above schemes are development of the teachers in the university.

III. QUALITY EDUCATION SCHEMES SPREAD AND REACH

Table 1: Reach of schemes of quality

S.N.	Name of the Programme	Number out of /Total (%)
1	UPE	16/795; (2.01%)
2	CPE	172/42338; (0.4%)
3	CPEPA	21/795; (2.64%)
4	SAP	816/ department no. unknown
5	Autonomous colleges	602/42338; (1.42%)
6	NAAC Assessment colleges	8853/42338; (20.9)
7	NAAC Assessment Universities	413/795; (51.94)
8	Research Projects: Major and Mino	1737/1470000; (0.1%)
9	ASC in XII Plan Period	2463300000/1470000(Rs.1675 per faculty in plan period Rs. 335 per year)

Source: UGC annual report 2016-17; NAAC annual report 2018-19

NAAC is launched in 1994 as scheme but later in 2012 it became quality assurance regulation. The function of NAAC to check the quality cell in all the university and verify this cell is coordinate all the activities of university and maintain and record of individuals staff. Performance appraisal of each faculty. It also guide the faculty members to improve activities and quality. The main role of this cell is to upload all the university reports in their website of their plan and development activities. As a result it helps to increase the grade point of quality assurance this is eligible for enhanced funding.

IV. API AS A MEASURE OF QUALITY IN HIGHER EDUCATION

Table 2: Comprehensiveness of API

S no	Goal of Higher Education	Strategies as mentioned in NPE	Academic performance indicators	Standards
1	Employability	Skill based courses	Category -1	Numeric value of
			Updating course	actual hours;, and
			content, teaching	number of students
			and evaluation	guided for M.Phil and
			Category -2,	Ph.D award
			career counseling,	
			corporate linkage,	
			Category -3	
			research guidance	
2	Quality	Minimum	NIL	NIL
		levels of		
		learning		
		training/	Category -2,	Numeric value of
		development	participation on	actual hours;
			seminars etc.	ISSN/ISBN;,,
			Category -3,	Funding amount;,,
			research projects	Policy document
			and publications	publication
		Teacher		
		appraisal	Embedded in the appraisal	
		Support for		
		research	NIL	NIL

Aip cover two goals of higher education

1. Employability

2. Quality

In employability Academic performance indicators has updating course content teaching and evaluation, career counseling and in standards numeric value of actual hours taken

In Quality as per NPE minimum level of learning, Teaching Training development should be taken. For the quality standards it required

V. CONCLUSION

As pr the discussion we can conclude that API is not a proper method to measure quality and performance of the teacher and institute in the higher education sector in india. with the support of the programmes and sectors the higher education are been changing fast and been well equipped. As per the need. performance of the teacher is flexible and there is a need of relook to concept of the performance appraisal in the higher education sector.

REFERENCES

- [1]. CABE (2018), Agenda for 65th meeting, Retrieved on 18/1/18 http://mhrd.gov.in/sites/upload_files/mhrd/files/AgendaHE_16012018.pdf
- [2]. Economic Times (2015), Accenture To Scrape Performance Reviews, 25 th July 2015
- [3]. Fabrice Henard and Soleine Leprince Ringuet (2008) The Path to Quality Teaching in Higher Education, OECD, Retrieved on 16/01/18 <https://www1.oecd.org/edu/imhe/44150246.pdf>
- [4]. Gupta Veera (2013) Policy Intents and Policy Instruments: A Case Study of CBSE; International Journal of Humanities and Applied Sciences (IJHAS) Vol. 2, No. 5, 2013 ISSN 2277 – 4386
- [5]. Noha Elassy, (2015) "The concepts of quality, quality assurance and quality enhancement", Quality Assurance in Education, Vol. 23 Issue: 3, pp.250-261, <https://doi.org/10.1108/QAE-11-2012-0046>
- [6]. Sanjay Singh Baroniya, Sanjay Gadge, Mamta Bhoj Baroniya and Harish Vyas (2014), Status of Academic Performance Indicator (API) for College Teachers of Madhya Pradesh: A Review, *Research Journal of Educational Sciences*, Vol. 2(5), 5-13, August 2014, ISSN 2321-0508

- [7]. Niti Aayog (2017) Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), Targets, CSS, Interventions, Nodal and other Ministries, Retrieved on 19/1/2018; http://niti.gov.in/writereaddata/files/SDGs%20V22-Mapping_August%202017.pdf
- [8]. National Policy of Education (1986) retrieved on 16/1/18 http://www.ncert.nic.in/oth_anoun/npe86.pdf
- [9]. OECD (2015), OECD Regulatory Outlook
- [10]. Planning Commission (2011) Twelfth Five Year Plan http://mhrd.gov.in/sites/upload_files/mhrd/files/document-reports/XIIFYP_SocialSector.pdf
- [11]. UGC (2010) Regulations on minimum qualifications for appointment of teachers and other academic staff in universities and colleges and measures for the maintenance of standards in higher education, Gazzete of India, Part III, Sector 4, (2010)
- [12]. UGC (2013) Indian Higher Education: Quest for Excellence, https://www.ugc.ac.in/pdfnews/7580771_Flag-ship-Programmes-of-UGC.pdf
- [13]. UGC, (No date) Schemes for Quality and Excellence; https://www.ugc.ac.in/pdfnews/3945983_Schemes-for-Qualiy-and-Excellence.pdf
- [14]. UGC (2016-17) Annual Report 2016-2017
- [15]. University of Washington, Sample offer letter for appointment, retrieved on 16/1/2018 <https://admin.artsci.washington.edu/offer-letter-sample-assistant-professor>.